

Total Information Awareness (TIA) *

Dr. John Poindexter^α, Dr. Robert Popp^α, Brian Sharkey^β
Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA)^α
Hicks and Associates Inc.^β

Abstract—The world has changed dramatically since the Cold War when there were two super powers. Then, it was relatively simple to identify our intelligence collection targets. It was sometimes hard to collect the intelligence, but the targets were clear. Today we live in a world of asymmetries. The most serious asymmetric threat facing the United States today is terrorism; a threat characterized by collections of loosely organized people who operate in shadowy networks that are difficult to identify and define and whose goal is the destruction of our way of life. The intelligence collection targets are thousands of people whose identities and whereabouts we do not always know.

If we are to preserve our national security, we must figure out a way of combating this threat. The solution is largely associated with information technology. We must become much more efficient and clever in the ways we use existing sources of data to find new sources of data, mine it for new information, generate context relevant information, make it widely available for collaborative analysis, convert it to knowledge and create actionable options for senior decision-makers. Also, we need a more systemic approach to the problem. A variety of tools, processes and procedures will be required to deal with this problem, however, to be effective, they must be integrated and harmonized within a system context built around a common architecture.

In this paper, we will provide a broad overview of the Total Information Awareness (TIA) program – a new counter terrorism initiative sponsored by the Information Awareness Office (IAO) at the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA). The TIA program will develop and integrate a variety of information technologies enabling early warning and understanding of terrorist activities and ultimately the preemption of terrorist attacks through collaborative decision making at the national security level. Examples of some of the key technologies needed for TIA include: entity and event detection and extraction, link discovery and pattern learning across space and time, human language exploitation including summarization and translation, biometrics and multi-modal techniques for human identification, various methods for privacy protection and policy formulation, and several prediction and estimation approaches to understand individual and

group behavior and intent. TIA will also require concepts and methods for bringing users with diverse points of view together in a collaborative problem-solving environment, where they can have access to their relevant data sources, the use of discovery tools and the ability to exploit and quickly generate models for structured arguments that facilitate the presentation and vetting of competing hypotheses.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

.....

- 1. INTRODUCTION
- 2. TIA SYSTEM OVERVIEW
- 3. TIA TECHNOLOGIES
- 4. THE IMPORTANCE OF MODELING
- 5. TIA SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION
- 6. SUMMARY

1. INTRODUCTION

Clearly, the most serious asymmetric threat facing the United States today is terrorism, a threat characterized by collections of loosely organized people who operate in shadowy networks and are difficult to define and identify. They are transnational in nature, move freely throughout the world, hide when necessary, find unpunished sponsorship and support, exploit safe harbors anywhere a modicum can be found, operate in small, independent cells, strike infrequently, and utilize weapons of mass effect and media response to influence governments.

If we are to preserve our national security, we must clearly define and develop methods to deal with the terrorist threat. TIA is our answer. The focus of TIA is to develop and integrate a variety of information technologies enabling early warning and understanding of terrorist activities and ultimately the preemption of terrorist attacks through collaborative decision making at the national security level.

A key concept underlying TIA is viewing the counter terrorism problem in a signal-processing context. In our view, if terrorist organizations are going to engage in adverse actions against the United States, it must involve people, and those people will make transactions, and those

Distribution Statement "A" (Approved for Public Release, Distribution Unlimited)
U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright.

Figure 1. TIA System Overview (Visionary)

transactions will leave a signature in the information space. Although terrorism is considered a low-intensity/low-density form of warfare, it does have an information signature, albeit not one that is easily detected. We think of the counter terrorism problem somewhat analogously to the signal processing problem found in anti-submarine warfare (ASW): in ASW, one is trying to find enemy submarines via acoustic signatures in an ocean of noise; in TIA, we're trying to find terrorist plans and activities via different types of information signatures in a world of information. In all cases, terrorists have left detectable clues – the significance of which however, are generally not understood until after an attack. Our goal in TIA is to develop information technology solutions that will allow analysts, policy makers, decision makers, and others to detect and understand these clues well prior to an attack so that appropriate measures can be taken to prevent further attacks from ever occurring.

2.0 TIA SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The problem of discovering plans and intent of potential terrorist activities is an information exploitation problem driven by the following key functional elements:

- Discovering terrorist identities through their physical presence or through signatures they leave in the information space
- Associating key entities (persona, activity events, transactions, etc.) with these identities

- Linking these identities and entity/activity events with other identities and entity/activity events
- Characterizing the behavior of individuals and groups from these activity events
- Vetting these association links and behavior characterizations among a group of analysts to promote alternative points of view and conclusions
- Conceptualizing any possible future states of these individuals and groups that may be harmful in order to enable early warning
- Developing and acting on probable mitigating and preemptive actions

From an implementation perspective, in order to achieve the above functions, the following technology themes apply (we are addressing each of these themes in our IAO programs):

- Biometrics to recognize and identify humans from a distance, determine whether or not their behaviors are deceptive, etc
- Data and human language translation and understanding to find and harvest new sources of information, structured/unstructured, in English and foreign languages, etc
- Data mining and link analysis to discover knowledge from various types of evidence, as well as weed out the noise within it

Figure 2. Human ID at a Distance (HID)

- Strategic analysis, knowledge discovery, and collaboration so that discovered patterns can be understood in the context of “behavior modes” that are argued within a structured, analytic, yet unconstrained, reasoning environment
- Predictive modeling to estimate plausible futures that can subsequently be converted into actionable intelligence and options for senior decision-makers
- Databases to allow appropriate and authorized access and querying of relevant data to discover evidence of patterns indicative of terrorist activity
- Security and privacy protection technologies so that laws, policies and regulations are adhered to with regard to the rights and protections of all citizens

Figure 1 presents an overview of TIA system, and we will describe it in more detail next. Before doing so, a couple of disclaimers. TIA is a visionary R&D prototype system concept for counter terrorism; it is not a system being used operationally today. TIA will allow various users within the *Intelligence, Counter Intelligence/Law Enforcement, Operations, and Policy* domains to experiment with different data, technology and operational concepts for counter terrorism. And lastly, technology components from TIA are being experimented with by operational elements with real world data available under existing laws and

policies to determine value-added to their missions. These components are not mining transactional or other data on US citizens which is prohibited by existing laws or policies.

Recall an earlier point: if terrorist organizations are going to engage in adverse actions against the United States, it will involve people at the atomic level, and those people will make transactions, and those transactions will leave a signature in the information space. These transactions can span many different information domains (e.g., financial, communications, travel, country entry/exit, etc) and live within databases owned by the public and private sector, government and commercial, DoD, intelligence, counter-intelligence, law enforcement, and others. Aside from the numerous policy and privacy protection challenges, a significant research challenge is determining which of these data sources, if any, is of value to exploit to discover and track terrorists.

There are other research challenges: (i) the sheer volume of the transaction space alone is daunting, (ii) given a pattern or model indicative of a terrorist plan or activity, it may be necessary to process a significant quantity of this transaction space to find the signals of interest (or, said differently, to weed out the noise), and finally (iii) there may be a variety of data acquisition, conditioning and compatibility issues impeding timely and accurate analysis. With this in mind, the goal is to extract and make the relevant information from these transactions available— as

allowed by existing laws and policies – with enhanced semantic content for easy analysis by the appropriate authorities.

For counter terrorism, the analytical environment is broader than just the intelligence community, but includes law enforcement, policy, operations, coalition partners and allies, outside experts, non-government organizations, and

Figure 3. Human Language Technology Programs

While our goal is total information awareness, there will always be uncertainty and ambiguity in trying to understand what is being planned. That is why tools in the collaborative multi-agency analytical environment must rely on models for context and a potential scenario that can frame competing hypotheses. Users and subject matter experts with diverse points of view will be brought together to analyze and solve problems collaboratively accessing and sharing data, as appropriate, and using various IT tools for discovery, understanding, model building, selection and refinement.

Collaboration environments have always been essential for resolving complex and diverse problems, especially when there are latent and error prone data with uncertain meaning. Today's technologies in the field of advanced distributed and asynchronous collaboration environments offer the promise to quickly connect together those highly qualified subject matter expert participants who have the experience for thinking through complex reasoning tasks in spite of these data uncertainties. Notably, however, additional tools will have to be made to allow the analysis process to be more efficient and to properly explore the multiple hypothesis space.

others. A similar collaborative multi-agency environment exists for the policy and operations community, but the functions are different. The mission here is to take the competing hypotheses from the analytical environment and estimate a range of plausible futures. The objective is to identify common nodes, representing situations that could occur, and to explore the probable impact of various actions or interventions that authorities might make in response to these situations.

A counter terrorism system like TIA requires a range of information technologies to be integrated in a systematic context. We have a number of projects in IAO to address this. The next section will describe these technologies.

3.0 TIA TECHNOLOGIES

Biometric Technologies

An initial component of the TIA system involves sensors and algorithms used for authentication and identification of people: the Human Identification at a Distance (HID) program. HID is developing technologies that exploit human biometrics as a method for providing unique identifiers for people. Further it is addressing active and passive methods for doing this and with the ambitious goal

of automating the authentication and identification process. Today, HID is focused primarily on face and gait – to detect, recognize and identify humans at great distances.

extraction, summarization, and translation technologies to enable English-speaking analysts to locate and interpret critical information in multiple foreign languages without requiring knowledge of those languages. The languages

Figure 4. Evidence Extraction and Link Discovery (EELD)

As shown in Figure 2, HID will also develop methods for fusing multi-modal biometric technologies together in a system sense, in order to exploit and make additive, the most opportunistic biometric features given the environment, the system construct and the human subject’s behavior. This can be characterized as an advanced human identification systems. Finally, HID will address and quantify the critical factors that affect performance of all relevant biometric components and identify their limits with regard to range, accuracy and reliability.

Human Language Technologies

An important category or class of components needed for the TIA system concept involves information discovery tools. The technologies from the Translingual Information Detection, Extraction, and Summarization (TIDES) program fall within this category (see Figure 3). There are limited numbers of English-speaking analysts in the national security community, with even fewer human translators that can translate foreign language documents, interpret useful segments into English and made available to the broader user community. This is unfortunately most prevalent in the languages of current interest given the geography of the perceived threat. Yet there’s a wealth of exploitable foreign speech and text that could prove itself extremely useful for analysis. The TIDES program is developing detection,

that TIDES is focused on are English, Arabic, and Chinese.

The Effective Affordable Reusable Speech-to-Text (EARS) program will also focus on human language discovery tools. EARS is developing automatic speech-to-text transcription technology whose output is substantially richer and more accurate than currently possible. EARS is exploiting various advanced natural language processing methods, meta-data, and feature extraction techniques to reduce the word error rate in broadcast and telephone conversation transcriptions to 5-10%. The current state-of-the-art is significantly worse. Like TIDES, EARS is also focused on English, Arabic, and Chinese.

Data Mining and Link Discovery Technologies

Another program that is focusing on discovery tools is the Evidence Extraction and Link Discovery (EELD) program. EELD is developing technologies for automated discovery, extraction and linking of sparse entity/event activities in large data sources. EELD detection capabilities are intended to extract relevant data and relationships about people, organizations and activities from unstructured and semi-structured message traffic and open source text data. As shown in Figure 4, the technologies will then link together related items that comprise potential terrorist groups or scenarios, and learn patterns of different groups

or scenarios to identify new organizations or emerging threats.

Much of the database technology used today was defined in the 1980s. But today's processors, disks, and networks are now orders of magnitude more capable. The database technology that is used by intelligence agencies, law

Figure 5. Strategic Analysis, Knowledge Discovery and Collaboration

Strategic Analysis, Knowledge Discovery, Collaboration

As Figure 5 depicts, Genoa II – a follow on to Genoa – will focus on the information technology support needed by teams of intelligence analysts and operations and policy personnel as they attempt to anticipate and preempt terrorist threats. Because the “source” data contain errors, ambiguities and latency, and, the analytic processing tools will have innate inefficiencies there will be uncertainty about the truth of detected entities, the links between them, and the conclusions that can be inferred. Needed are faster systems of humans and machines, ways to overcome the biases and limitations of the human cognitive system, and “cognitive amplifiers” that help teams of people rapidly and deeply understand complicated and uncertain situations. Genoa II will apply automation to team processes so that more can be accomplished sooner. It will also develop and deploy cognitive aids that allow humans and machines to think together about complicated problems. And lastly it will enable the breaking down of today’s information stovepipes by creating a dynamic, adaptable, peer-to-peer collaborative environment that supports the necessary co-existence of hierarchical and network organizations.

enforcement and the military today is lacking in its ability to support an effective defense to terrorism. This is due in part to several reasons, including: an inability to access and exploit – automatically and as appropriate – the relevant structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data from many different and non-traditional database sources, and an inability to easily create new information repositories in a timely manner which today exist only in manual form.

A central component of the TIA system is the Genisys program, which will focus on the reinvention of database technology as was just discussed. Genisys will also explore a variety of privacy protection technologies, including: data anonymization of sources and subjects, selective revelation of data, use of “dumb” agents rather than humans to search, enforcement of rigorous access controls and permissioning techniques, partitioning of information, justification and authorization for queries, and creation of a credible tamper-proof audit trail available to oversight authority.

4.0 THE IMPORTANCE OF MODELS

Discovery and understanding of any data or information requires a frame of reference that provides the context and

semantics. This frame of reference is captured in some form of model that we use to guide the process information gathering and of hypothesis validation through observation of the collected evidence. In the case of TIA, these models, heuristic, empirical or analytic, apply to the description of entities, links, group and organizational topologies and behavior characterizations that is being explored. Because of the centrality of the need to use models, DARPA is exploring several programs that exploit novel types of models that are focused on assisting with early warning of terrorist activity. We will now describe a few of these.

Predictive Modeling Technologies

The Wargaming the Asymmetric Environment (WAE) program is developing promising predictive technology to better anticipate and act against terrorists. WAE identifies predictive indicators of terrorist-specific attacks and behaviors by examining their behavior in the broader context of their political, cultural and ideological environment. WAE has developed, in conjunction with DoD and the intelligence community, indication and warning models for select terrorist individuals and organizations. These models have been tested historically and in some cases used successfully operationally to predict an active terrorist group's next action with regard to attack/no attack, target characteristics, location characteristics, tactical characteristics, timeframes, and motivating factors.

Bio-Surveillance Technologies

As part of the TIA system requirement for developing models, the Bio-Surveillance program is exploring the value of non-traditional statistical data sources (e.g., over-the-counter sales of medications, grocery store purchases, school absenteeism, etc.) to automatically detect and warn of a covert release of a biological pathogen earlier than possible using traditional ailing patient of fatality diagnostic approaches. Early detection and warning is key to mitigating the effects of a biological attack. Given the availability of appropriate medications, it has been suggested that as many as half the expected casualties could be prevented if an attack is detected only a few days earlier than it otherwise would have been. For contagious biological agents, early detection is clearly paramount. This program is also developing privacy protection technology.

Structured Argumentation Technologies

Human collaboration has become a structural requirement for all tasks that we perform. No single individual has all the sufficient knowledge and expertise to counter the terrorist threat. To be effective, each of us performs better when working together with others as a collaborative team tasked with achieving a common goal. Members of the team are usually selected based on experience and expertise in the domain of interest, but also to create diversity of thinking so that alternative points of view are considered when

achieving a good working solution. The process of reasoning about the meaning of uncertain data is an exact model for TIA analysts and decision makers. In our opinion, two technologies are fundamentally required; (i) peer-to-peer and center-based collaboration environments that can quickly assemble the right people, with the data and tools for performing analysis, and (ii) methods for structuring the analysis, vetting and decision making process of the collaborating group.

Structure argumentation is a method for breaking the elements of the analysis into a form that is ordered and readily understandable from a logic or evidential reasoning perspective. It provides a basis for proving a hypothesis by exposing the evidence associated with an argument that is postulated. The hypothesis can be viewed as a "model" of the argument to be proved, the data is the evidence, and the structured argument is formalism for coupling the data to the model as a way of proving that the evidence supported the model.

TIA is exploiting many several structured argument technologies. Figure 5 illustrates several modeling tools for structuring and reasoning about the data. Our goal to be able to make these models available to analysts and decision makers within collaborative environments that are compartmentalized based on specific problems being considered.

5.0 TIA SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The TIA system implementation that we've employed is a two-pronged, yet integrated, approach consisting of:

- A rapid prototyping activity designed to quickly assess candidate component technologies within an experimental context using real analysts solving real problems with real data as allowed by existing law and policy.
- An assured transition activity that will continuously insert proven (in a metrics-based performance sense) technologies into a "hardened" leave-behind and permanently sustainable system.

TIA is being developed along two parallel paths, i.e., at the component-level and the system-level. In both paths, we are using open emerging standards and a spiral development process that will allow the early insertion of new components and refresh of existing components as applicable. For component-level testing, we will use synthetic data with simulated terrorist signals embedded, allowing us to test the components yet avoid privacy issues. For system-level testing, we will use real world data permitted by existing law and policy, using a three-month experimental cycle. Incremental transition of components is occurring to operational systems. These technology

components allow operational users to more efficiently analyze data sources they already have.

The “end state” for TIA system is a networked system of systems spanning four domains, namely, *intelligence*, *counter intelligence/law enforcement*, *operations*, and *policy*. In our view, to successfully provide early warning and preemption of terrorist activities, the system requires presence and data sharing within and across each of these domains. We are currently working with customers in each of these domains. We have created a TIA testbed network using commercial collaboration software running over a secure VPN on top of an operational network that spans these domains. This testbed has allowed us to work with geographically distributed operational users to test and assess our prototype technology in the context of their real-world problems using their real-world data, obtained and shared in accordance with existing laws and policies. We have also conducted three TIA experiments to date over this testbed. The focus has mainly been to test the collaborative environment as well as assess several components from past and ongoing DARPA programs.

“Red-Team” Activities

TIA must be intended to operate under a broad range of threat scenarios associated with asymmetric methods that can be used for terrorist acts. Quantitative testing the TIA system to assess performance is difficult because there is no existing set of “truth” data available to test all possible scenarios. Thus we will engage in the use of “red-teams” (more specifically *adaptive red- teams*) that can act as pseudo-real threats through the introduction of artificial threat data into the mix of a real-world background noise data. Since scenarios are a form of describing a plausible future states for the system, red-team scenarios are then also useful for establishing an initial set of models from which to begin creation of hypotheses and structuring arguments. Our intention for TIA is to use red-teams for both the establishment of a set of initial threat scenarios for the purpose of supporting the task of building models, and for the alternative process to test and thwart the system by introducing variants of these scenarios.

6.0 SUMMARY

We believe that total information awareness (TIA) is an important yet very difficult to achieve capability required for addressing the problem of early warning and preemption of terrorist activity. The TIA program is in the tradition of the very hard problems that DARPA has addressed in the past. We think we have structured the TIA program to

conceptualize a broad and novel view of collaborative data sharing with tools to be used in a structured manner to address the critical needs of today analysts and decision makers. It is our view that the ultimate solution to countering terrorism requires a co-evolution in four areas: technology, process/operations, policy, and culture. Our focus is on developing the technology, the first area, and making sure that decisions in the other areas, such as policy, are knowledgeable about what is possible and what isn't. It's an exciting area, and we are proud to be part of the community who are making contributions to enhance national security.

BIOGRAPHIES

Dr. John Poindexter is Director of the Information Awareness Office (IAO) of the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA). Dr. Poindexter, a nuclear physicist, is responsible for guiding and directing the development of information awareness programs and will oversee the IAO information projects, comprising a broad spectrum of innovative technologies that will significantly influence future national security missions. Dr. Poindexter recently worked for SYNTEK Technologies where, as Senior Vice President, he was responsible for providing high legal advice on management and direction of information systems projects, including DARPA's Project Genoa. Dr. Poindexter is also a retired US naval officer who served President Reagan as his National Security Advisor.

Dr. Robert Popp is the Deputy Director of the Information Awareness Office (IAO) of the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA). Dr. Popp, a Computer Scientist and Electrical Engineer, assists the Director of IAO in guiding and directing the various programs within the office that are addressing future asymmetric threats and other national security concerns. Prior to joining DARPA, Dr. Popp served as the Assistant Deputy Under Secretary of Defense in the Advanced Systems and Concepts (AS&C) office within the office of the Secretary of Defense (OSD).

Mr. Brian Sharkey is a Senior Vice President of the Advanced Systems and Concepts Office of Hicks and Associates Inc. (a wholly owned SAIC Corporation). He is has prior experience developing technologies and systems for DARPA and other DOD organizations and was a former Deputy Director of DARPA's Information Systems Office.